

Flexible Large-Area Light-Emitting Devices Based on WS₂ Monolayers

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Strong covalent in-plane bonds and a tiny thickness in the nanometer range make two-dimensional (2D) materials ideally suited for flexible electronic or optoelectronic applications. Despite this exciting perspective, only a few prototypes of such flexible devices—photodetectors and transistors—have been reported until now. The first large-area flexible light-emitting device (LED) based on 2D materials is realized by integrating a transition metal dichalcogenide (TMDC) monolayer synthesized by metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) into a p–n architecture on conductive polymer foil. This flexible LED demonstrates homogeneous red light emission from a few square millimeter area in a scalable design. Uniquely, the electroluminescence can be tuned over 30 meV simply by bending the devices, i.e., by applying a defined strain. This approach combines the flexibility of organic semiconductor device concepts with the durability of inorganic semiconductor technology.

Using mechanically flexible substrates for complex (opto-)electronic device architectures is of growing interest in the area of consumer electronics,^[1] for wearables^[2] or for applications in biology and life science.^[3] Potential candidates for light-emitting devices (LEDs) on curved or flexible surfaces are organic LEDs (OLEDs)^[4] or quantum dot LEDs^[5,6] (QD-LEDs). Higher durability is achieved by bottom-up approaches, which combine individual inorganic micro-LEDs to flexible arrays.^[1,3] Although two-dimensional (2D) materials are ideally suited for flexible device applications,^[7–9] only a few flexible prototype devices such as transistors^[10–12] or photodetectors^[13–15] have

been reported until now. The implementation of transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) as prototype 2D semiconductors beyond graphene in different kinds of devices on foil substrates—such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET) or polyimide—has been demonstrated using exfoliated materials,^[10,12,15] chemical vapor deposition (CVD) layers^[11,14] or solution processed layers on wafer scale^[13] with device areas ranging from μm^2 up to cm^2 scale.^[14] Until now, just one attempt was made toward TMDC light emitters on a flexible substrate: Withers et al.^[16] realized a $7 \mu\text{m}^2$ stack based on exfoliated materials on a PET substrate exhibiting electroluminescence (EL). An industrial up-scaling of this approach, however, is not feasible. Most important, a tunability of the emission wavelength with applied strain—as predicted in literature^[17]—has not yet been demonstrated in any electrically driven device based on 2D materials. In this work, we realized a mechanically flexible and scalable LED based on a WS₂ monolayer grown in a commercial AIXTRON hot-wall metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) reactor in 10×2 ” configuration. By adopting a vertical LED stack we inherently overcome limitations in scalability^[16,18] and the emissive area is primarily limited by our layout which consists of four individual LEDs defined on a $1 \times 1 \text{cm}^2$ conductive substrate. Importantly, the emission wavelength can be tuned over a wide range by bending the device, i.e., by applying a defined strain.

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We have chosen indium tin oxide (ITO) coated polyethylene naphthalate (PEN) foil as bendable substrate due to its chemical resistance and thermal stability in conjunction with its high transparency in the visible spectral range.^[19] The concept of the fabricated LED is illustrated in **Figure 1a** and represents a scalable, vertical architecture. The ITO-coated PEN foil acts as transparent anode with a nominal sheet resistance of 15 Ohm sq^{-1} (VisionTek Systems Ltd. supplier information). Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS) and poly[*N,N'*-bis(butylphenyl)-*N,N'*-bis(phenyl)benzidine] (poly-TPD) are spin-coated on top as organic hole injection and hole transport layer/electron blocking layer, respectively. The luminescent layer is a three-atom-thick WS₂ monolayer with a room temperature photoluminescence (PL) emission around 2.04 eV. The fully coalesced TMDC monolayer has been grown by MOCVD on a 2” sapphire (0001) wafer and

Figure 1. Device concept and electrical characteristics. a) p–n device architecture on ITO-coated foil substrate with monolayer WS₂ synthesized by metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) as active material, organic hole injection (PEDOT:PSS) and hole transport layers (poly-TPD), and a ZnO-NP layer on the cathode side. b) *I*–*V* characteristics measured three times in forward and reverse bias, respectively, showing a rectifying ratio above 100 at ±3 V.

was transferred on top of the poly-TPD layer using a polystyrene auxiliary layer in a semi-dry approach^[20] with modifications as described in the Supporting Information (Device Preparation). A layer of ZnO nanoparticles (NP) is spin-coated on top of the active material and serves as electron injection/transport layer as well as hole blocking layer. Finally, aluminum pads were evaporated through a shadow mask to form the cathodes and simultaneously define the active device areas. Scaling up to TMDC wafer size could be performed by increasing the cathode size.

By applying a voltage, charge carriers are injected into the active material where they recombine with photon emission in the red spectral region. For a good device performance, three main characteristics are important: First, the device is designed to perform like a p–n diode due to the p-type behavior of the hole injection and transport layers and the n-type characteristics of the ZnO-NP layer. Second, these p- and n-type layers are expected to reduce the potential barriers between the electrodes and the conduction and valence band of the WS₂ monolayer, respectively, enabling low-voltage operation. Third, the

band offsets should lead to a blocking behavior of poly-TPD and ZnO-NPs for electrons and holes, respectively, which is important to confine the charge carriers to the active layer and increase the recombination rate. The operation principle and energy levels are given by a schematic diagram in Figure S1 (Supporting Information).

The *I*–*V* characteristics of the flexible device are depicted in Figure 1b, demonstrating the expected rectifying behavior. The samples possess stable and reproducible current–voltage characteristics in three consecutive measurements in forward and reverse direction, respectively. The rectification ratio of the current densities for positive and negative voltages of more than 100 at ±3 V confirms the assumption of a diode-like behavior and low leakage currents. This can also be observed in a linear plot of the *I*–*V* curve (Figure S2, Supporting Information). The current density in the range of several 0.1 A cm^{−2} at 7 V is in good agreement with literature data for μm²-sized TMDC-based vertical light emitters^[16] and typical QD-LEDs.^[21]

Upon applying a forward bias to the fabricated device, red EL can be observed. Voltage-dependent EL spectra are shown in Figure 2a, demonstrating pronounced emission clearly originating from the WS₂ monolayer. The slight shift in peak wavelength—compared to the PL signal of the as-grown WS₂ monolayer on sapphire (see Figure S3, Supporting Information)—might have different reasons. In previous works it has been shown that the PL peak shifts after the transfer of TMDC layers from the sapphire substrate into the device environment due to the change of the adjacent material and thus the dielectric environment^[20,22] (see also Figure S3, Supporting Information). In addition, the emission energy can be influenced by built-in fields of the p–n junction, by the external electric fields when applying a bias voltage and—in particular—by emerging Joule heating effects with increasing current density. The shift of the EL peak position from 640 nm at 3 V (some 10 mA cm^{−2}) to about 652 nm at 6.5 V (≈350 mA cm^{−2}) would correspond to a temperature increase of about 105 K, calculated with a bandgap decrease of −0.34 meV K^{−1} for the WS₂ monolayer grown by MOCVD, if Joule heating effects are dominant. The value of −0.34 meV K^{−1} was determined from the nearly linear part of a Varshni fit of temperature dependent EL measurements for a reference device on a glass substrate as shown in Figure S4 (Supporting Information). An excellent turn-on voltage of <3 V can be determined as indicated by the distinct EL signal detected at 3 V (see inset of Figure 2a).

The EL intensity raises with increasing voltage, as shown in Figure 2b. The inset depicts the luminance versus current density, showing a significant rise in light emission above a current density of approximately 10 mA cm^{−2}. At an applied voltage of 3 V, the LED emits with a luminance of about 5 × 10^{−4} cd m^{−2} which continuously increases reaching a value of nearly 1 cd m^{−2} at a voltage of 9 V. In the red spectral region, this value corresponds to a radiance of about 1 μW sr^{−1} cm^{−2}. Taking into account that the internal quantum efficiency of these WS₂ monolayers was previously estimated to be about 10^{−2}%^[20] and could be improved by further optimizing the growth process, our device architecture has the potential to achieve brightness values exceeding the technically relevant number of 1000 cd m^{−2}. These EL and luminance measurements were performed on unstrained devices under ambient conditions, i.e., without any encapsulation.

Figure 2. Optoelectronic performance of a flexible two-dimensional (2D) light-emitting device (LED). a) Electroluminescence (EL) spectra at different voltages taken from an unstrained device. Inset: EL spectrum detected at a voltage of 3 V. b) Luminance and radiance versus applied voltage in a semilogarithmic diagram. Inset: Luminance L_V as function of the induced current density plotted on a logarithmic scale. c) Photograph of a fabricated device on a 1×1 cm² PEN foil substrate, bent between two fingers. d) Optical image of a bent device—fixed between two clamp jaws—emitting red light from a 6 mm² pad at an applied voltage of 4.5 V (scale bar 2 mm).

To demonstrate the potential of the device flexibility, a 2D LED on a 1×1 cm² PEN foil substrate is bent between two fingers in Figure 2c. The four active pads, formed by the aluminum cathodes, have a size of 6 mm² each. A photograph of an operating flexible LED is given in Figure 2d at an applied voltage of 4.5 V in the bent state, which highlights that the deformation does not affect the macroscopic behavior of the device. Even in bent state, almost homogeneous light emission in the red spectral region over the whole active area is observed. The slight inhomogeneities of intensity in the active area might be related to wrinkle formation during transfer, leading to a non-ideal contact between the WS₂ monolayer and the underlying poly-TPD. Note that the EL did not significantly change when storing the device in a N₂ box for a period of more than 10 months after first use.

In contrast to the luminescent material of flexible OLEDs^[23] or QD-LEDs,^[5,6] WS₂ is a 2D crystal extending in the lateral plane. Simple bending of a WS₂-based device thus causes uniaxial strain in the WS₂ crystal and thereby offers an exciting route for tuning its emission wavelength. Conversely, measuring the EL shift can be used to determine the bending radius. In order

to demonstrate emission wavelength tuning by device bending, the flexible LED is clamped between two stamps, which can be moved up- and downwards with micrometer screws. By varying the height s , a precise adjustment of the bending radius and thus a defined uniaxial strain can be applied, as indicated by the sketch in Figure 3a. More information on the strain determination is given in the Supporting Information (Strain Calculation, Figure S5, Supporting Information).

Applying a uniaxial force means that a WS₂ 2D layer of length L is compressed or extended in one of its in-plane directions by ΔL , resulting in a variation of the covalent bond lengths. The resulting strain, defined by $\varepsilon = \Delta L/L$, is negative for compressive strain and positive for tensile strain. In our design, the fabricated LED is on the inner side of the bent substrate, which implies compressive strain in the active WS₂ monolayer. The critical strain for ITO affecting its conductivity is higher for a compression (around -1.7%) than for an extension (around 1.1%)^[24] which is why this approach has been chosen.

A strain-induced change of the bandgap for TMDCs has been calculated in detail in literature.^[17,25] Theory predicts a bandgap

Figure 3. Strain-dependent electroluminescence. a) Schematic illustration of the measurement setup and calculation of the induced compressive in-plane strain on the WS₂ monolayer. b) Electroluminescence (EL) spectra for different applied values of compressive strain—from 0% (blue) to -1% (red)—recorded at 3 V and 59 mA cm⁻², respectively. c) EL peak position and energy shift versus applied strain ε (colored dots). Gray dashed line: linear fit with a slope of $-(30.2 \pm 4.7)$ meV $\varepsilon(\%)^{-1}$.

reduction for uniaxial tensile strain and a bandgap increase for uniaxial compressive strain with a nearly linear gauge factor. However, in these calculations, the value of the monolayers WS_2 gauge factor covers a relatively large interval between $-11 \text{ meV } \varepsilon(\%)^{-1}$ ^[26] and $-50 \text{ meV } \varepsilon(\%)^{-1}$ ^[25]. Experimentally, such a strain-induced change of the bandgap has only been confirmed for tensile strain in monolayers by an energy shift observed in PL or absorption measurements.^[25–27]

In Figure 3b normalized EL spectra are plotted for different values of applied compressive strain ranging from 0% (blue) to -1% (red). Compressive strain far above -1% leads to short-circuits in the device due to cracks in the ITO. All spectra are taken at an applied voltage of 3 V in order to exclude thermal effects due to Joule heating. During this experiment, the current density remained constant at a value of 59 mA cm^{-2} independent of the applied strain. It is obvious that the maximum peak position shifts toward lower wavelengths with increasing compressive strain, while the full width at half maximum (FWHM) remains virtually constant with a value of $46.3 \pm 1.6 \text{ nm}$. A blue shift of -10.2 nm is obtained at -1% strain with respect to zero strain. We found a linear relation between EL peak shift and compressive strain (see Figure 3c) with a gauge factor of $-(30.2 \pm 4.7) \text{ meV } \varepsilon(\%)^{-1}$, which is in reasonably good agreement with the strain-dependent PL data for these devices (see Figure S6, Supporting Information). While this result corresponds well with the values expected from theory, a comparison with experimentally determined gauge factors is instructive. For exfoliated WS_2 monolayers values of $-46 \text{ meV } \varepsilon(\%)^{-1}$ ^[27] and $-50 \text{ meV } \varepsilon(\%)^{-1}$ ^[25] have been determined by analyzing PL and absorption measurements, while a value of $-11 \text{ meV } \varepsilon(\%)^{-1}$ is found for CVD monolayers.^[26] Naively, this difference might be attributed to the polycrystalline nature of the CVD layers, in which strain might be released more effectively at grain boundaries. However, it has been shown that strain can be transferred across grain boundaries in MoS_2 monolayers synthesized by CVD,^[28] and Raman data do not confirm a reduced strain within WS_2 crystallites grown by CVD.^[26] The comparatively large gauge factor of $-(30.2 \pm 4.7) \text{ meV } \varepsilon(\%)^{-1}$ found here indicates that strain significantly affects the emission wavelength in spite of the polycrystalline nature of the coalesced WS_2 monolayer in our devices. It is worth mentioning that the process of wavelength tuning by bending is reversible. After 1000 bending cycles with a compressive strain of approximately -0.5% the EL peak wavelength does not change noticeably as shown in Figure S7 (Supporting Information). Thus, our findings open a path to use strain engineering to control the emission wavelength in a TMDC-based LED.

In conclusion, the first flexible LED has been developed employing 2D materials as an active layer. Our approach is scalable and based on a vertical p–n architecture with ITO-coated PEN foil as flexible substrate. For fabrication of the active layers, growth of fully coalesced WS_2 monolayers has been performed by MOCVD on 2" sapphire wafers and the WS_2 monolayers were implemented into the LED by a semi-dry transfer process. The devices show the expected diode-like behavior in their I – V characteristics. Applying a bias voltage of 6.5 V leads to red light emission with a wavelength of 652 nm over the whole active area of 6 mm^2 . Starting with a turn-on voltage $< 3 \text{ V}$, the devices reach a luminance of approximately

1 cd m^{-2} at 9 V. The strong dependence of the WS_2 bandgap on strain results in a tunable EL emission with a gauge factor of $-(30.2 \pm 4.7) \text{ meV } \varepsilon(\%)^{-1}$ simply by bending the device. This work proves the large potential of TMDC monolayers for ultrathin, scalable, and flexible optoelectronics, in which changes of the bending radius can be precisely monitored by a corresponding wavelength shift.

Experimental Section

Experimental details are available in the Supporting Information.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords

2D semiconductors, electroluminescence, flexible devices, light-emitting devices, MOCVD, transition metal dichalcogenides, WS_2 monolayers

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